

Calibration-based assessment of molecular formula assignment accuracy in UHRMS analysis of humic substances using a flavonoid reference material

Byvsheva S.M.¹, Volkov D.S.¹

¹Chemistry Department, M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia, sophia.byvsheva@gmail.com

Keywords: high-resolution mass-spectrometry, natural organic matter, accuracy, internal calibration
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17318884

The primary method for analyzing the molecular composition of natural organic matter (NOM) is high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS). Obtaining accurate and reproducible data on the molecular composition of NOM samples is essential for addressing environmental chemistry problems. Calibration is a key step in achieving high mass accuracy. Internal calibration can be performed using the detection of known compounds within the sample. However, due to the limited information available on compounds present in NOM, calibration solutions can be added and mixed with the sample prior to analysis.

Commercially available reference materials (RM) of natural compounds were used as external standards and added to Suwannee River fulvic acid (SRFA) solutions. The RM included flavonoids, which are common in nature and share molecular formulas with ions found in humic substances (HS). Three types of spectra were recorded: (i) without internal calibration, (ii) with internal calibration using the mass 212.075074, corresponding to *N*-butylbenzenesulfonamide (a plasticizer from tubing used in gas transfer to the mass spectrometer), and (iii) with internal calibration using ions from a standard flavonoid solution added to SRFA. In total, 20 spectra were obtained, with two replicates for each spectrum type, collected at equal time intervals. Both approaches to internal calibration (Figure 1, A and B) resulted in improved accuracy compared to spectra recorded without internal calibration (Figure 1, C). For single-ion calibration, a decrease in reproducibility was observed for ions with high *m/z* values, whereas for calibration with 10 ions, reproducibility was consistent across the entire *m/z* range, with 3σ not exceeding 0.5 ppm. Analysis of Shewhart charts and the calculation of metrological characteristics for 21 analyte ions confirmed the advantages of using internal calibration with 10 ions.

Figure 1. Mass accuracy plots for 21 analytical ions (black line – μ (mean mass error), grey line – 3σ and -3σ (σ – standard deviation): A - without internal calibration, B - with internal calibration using one mass, C - with internal calibration using 10 masses, corresponding to ions present in a standard solution of flavonoids added to SRFA.

Acknowledgements. The work was supported by the Russian Science Foundation, project number 21-73-20202.